

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE EFFECT OF SNAGS VERSUS DEEP TRANSVERSE FRICTION MASSAGE ON THE STUDENTS WITH MECHANICAL NECK PAIN AND MOBILITY DEFICIT

Sonam Nidhi

Assistant Professor, Department of Physiotherapy,

Teerthanker Mahaveer University, India

ORCID id: 0009-0008-0165-3763

Sunny Kumar

Consultant Physiotherapy,

School of Physiotherapy,

Moradabad, UP India

ORCID id: 0009-0001-7790-1056

ABSTRACT

Objective: The study was done to find out the difference between the effect of two manual therapies i.e., SNAG's and DTFM, on patients with mechanical neck pain and mobility deficit.

Method: The study was of an experimental design, with 30 subjects, and all subjects were assigned into two groups, 15 subjects in each, according to criteria (inclusion & exclusion) and carried out at physiotherapy OPD of Teerthanker Mahaveer University Hospital. In both groups, disability & pain were assessed by using the NDI & NBQ score respectively. The collected data were of mean and standard deviation of NDI & NBQ score and has been analysed using SPSS software. Paired T-test was used to find the difference between two groups.

Results: The results showed that there was significant difference in pain and disability with their NDI and NBQ score ($p=0.000$).

Conclusion: The study finds that group B, or deep friction Friction massage therapy, reduced pain and disability more than SNAGs, as evidenced by the difference in BQ and NDI from the first to the 21st day (Table No. 4-4) for both groups/therapies.

A Comparative Study on The Effect of Snags Versus Deep Transverse Friction Massage on The Students with Mechanical Neck Pain and Mobility Deficit

Keywords: Mechanical Neck Pain; SNAG's (Sustained Natural Apophyseal Glides); DTFM (Deep Transverse Friction Massage); NDI (Neck Disability Index) & NBQ (Neck Bournemouth Questionnaire).

Cite this Article: Sonam Nidhi and Sunny Kumar, A Comparative Study on The Effect of Snags Versus Deep Transverse Friction Massage on The Students with Mechanical Neck Pain and Mobility Deficit, *International Journal of Physiotherapy (IJPH)* 2(2), 2024, pp. 1–10, <https://iaeme.com/Home/issue/IJPH?Volume=2&Issue=2>

BACKGROUND

An ache that originates in the neck and may radiate down one or both arms is known as neck pain. The following symptoms are linked to mechanical neck pain: headache (65%), upper limb pain (80%), upper back pain (64%), lower back pain (39%), dizziness (31%), and nausea (23%).^[1] Mechanical neck pain is defined as pain arising from overuse of a characteristic anatomical structure or discomfort resulting from damage or deformation of an anatomical structure. 45–54% of the general population experiences mechanical neck pain at some point in their lives, and it can lead to severe disorders.^[2]

The restriction of the cervical joint's range of motion in mechanical neck pain is closely associated with discomfort that is followed by a little positioning error in the guarding muscles of the levator scapulae, cervical paravertebral, and upper trapezius.^[3] Most cases of mechanical neck pain occur in adults. Its origins are multifaceted. While the precise aetiology of neck pain remains uncertain, risk factors for neck discomfort include ageing, strain, hard lifting, prolonged employment, bad posture, and mental distress.^[4]

It has been demonstrated that high levels of physical exercise indicate the maintenance of mobility. Mobility status and physical activity level seem to be somewhat different as indicators of mortality.^[5] SNAG mobilisation is often performed in a sitting or standing posture. Active movement is used to sustain glides on the facet, which are then overpressed until the joint returns to its initial placement.^[6] The NDI is now widely used by researchers and physicians to measure the self-rated impairment caused by neck discomfort. A score of 0–5 is assigned to each of the 10 items. Thus, 50 is the highest possible score. According to this system, a score between 5 and 14 (10–28%) was deemed to represent mild disability, between 15 and 24 (30–48%) a moderate disability, between 25 and 38 (50–68%) a severe disability, and, finally, over 34 (68%) a complete disability.^[7]

James Cyriax developed it empirically, and it's currently applied in rehabilitative settings. In sports medicine, the transverse, or Cyriax, method of DFM is frequently employed.^[18]

The most common upper extremity and shoulder pain concerns documented in the literature related to smartphone addiction are those involving the wrist, neck, upper back, and lower back. Because of the increased angle of flexion of the cervical vertebrae caused by smartphone use, the neck region is said to be one of the most susceptible to musculoskeletal issues. Further suggested that the features of gait are affected by smartphone use.^[9] The limitation of distribution-based techniques is that, as statistical measurements, they do not yield a reliable indicator of the clinical significance of the observed change.^[20] Daily living tasks like personal hygiene, lifting, reading, working, driving, sleeping, and engaging in recreational activities are among the topics covered in the questions.^[21]

Although DTFM can help with pain management and range of motion, there isn't any high-quality research to back up its application in patients.²² The study of nociceptive pain processing in various musculoskeletal pain syndromes has drawn more attention in recent years.²³

TESTING PROCEDURE-

- An experimental study will be conducted for college going students in and around Moradabad, Uttar Pradesh
- By using convenient sampling technique, 30 participants of age 16- 25 years will be selected who will meet the inclusion criteria.
- Prior to participation, informed consent form will be taken from each individual. The study will be thoroughly explained to all subjects.
- Subjects who fulfilled inclusion and exclusion criteria were equally divided into two groups by random sampling method.
- 30 participants having mechanical Neck Pain and mobility deficit were available for the study and later divided into two equal halves of size 15 that constituted into two groups and further designated as “Group A” and “Group B”. The patients with mechanical Neck Pain and mobility deficit in Group A received SNAG’S Mobilization and Conservative physiotherapy treatment while rest of other patients of group B received DTFM.
- The patients assessed by NDI scale, Neck Bourn meth Questionnaire and AROM analysis at baseline and were treated for 3 weeks and reassessed by the same. NDI scales and Neck Bourn meth Questionnaire have been shown to be reliable and valid.

INTERVENTION FLOW CHART

DATA ANALYSIS

Table no. 1-Mean, standard deviation for the difference (pre & Post)

SL. No.	Variables	Group1(Mean±SD)	Group2(Mean±SD)
1	NDI	8.06±0.745	7.66±1.839
2	BQ	14.53±0.008	25.26±5.551
3	ROM(F)	3.67±0.716	5.66±1.5
4	ROM(EX)	2.00±0.649	4.00±2.13
5	ROM(LF)	5.67±2.021	4.34±0.9
6	ROM(R)	4.34±1.513	8.34±0.584

Table no. 2-% improvement b/ w (pre & post) in B.Q. SCORES, N.D.I. scores & ROM in group 1 & group 2

SL. No.	Types of Scores	Group1	Group2	Difference in % between the groups
1	NDI	45.97%	53.45%	7.48%
2	BQ	37.32%	63.57%	26.25%
3	ROM(F)	9.91%	15.43%	5.52%
4	ROM(EX)	4.65%	12.92%	8.27%
5	ROM(LF)	14.41%	10.76%	3.65%
6	ROM(R)	7.70%	18.00%	10.30%

Graph1.-The Bar chart of average values of ROM at pre & post in two groups

A Comparative Study on The Effect of Snags Versus Deep Transverse Friction Massage on The Students with Mechanical Neck Pain and Mobility Deficit

Graph 2.-The Bar chart of average difference b/ w pre & post for B.Q. score, N.D.I. score & ROM in two groups

Graph 3.-The Percentage difference from (pre & post)day in two groups for B.Q. score, N.D.I.score & ROM

RESULT

Thirty samples were used in the current investigation for the comparative analysis. The Teerthanker Mahaveer University in Moradabad provided the samples used in this instance. The NDI and BOURNEMOUTH QUESTINNAIRE are the nominal data that we used in our research.

The data collected for this investigation were analysed statically using several tests.

The data were analysed using the mean, standard deviation, and paired T-test.

The results indicate a significant difference in each group at the 5% level of significance ($P < .05$) Table 5.

Additionally, group B's BQ score rose by 13.8% compared to the NDI score of 12.7%. It is clear that the BQ score was superior to the NDI score.

DISCUSSION

The findings indicate that compared to equivalent models based on numerical variables, the functional models have a significantly tighter association with the NDI scale. (24)

In this study, patients with persistent mechanical neck pain were examined to examine the association between pain, disability, and range. In their 2019 study, Reddy et al. discovered a strong positive correlation between the level of neck pain and position sense inaccuracy in those who experienced it. Our research did not reveal a relationship between cervical proprioception and neck pain. Like our research, Lee et al.'s 2008 study found no connection between the degree of neck pain and the subjects' cervical proprioceptive awareness in those with chronic neck pain. (25)

The treatment of mechanical neck pain improved significantly in both groups, according to the Amin FS study; however, the Mulligan mobilization group was able to increase the cervical joint's range of motion, reduce pain, and lessen the patients' disability more successfully. To put it briefly, MMT combined with traditional physiotherapy works better for treating MNP than traditional physiotherapy by itself. (26)

It was determined that individuals with chronic mechanical neck pain who underwent stretching exercises or at-home exercise programs would have less pain and have better cervical spine range of motion and chest expansion. Nonetheless, compared to a home exercise program, a passive stretching exercise program improved cervical active range of motion and chest expansion. (27) Additionally, it might lessen the weight on the cervical spine, lessen the mechanical stress transmitted on it, and lessen pain. (28)

CONCLUSION

The research demonstrates that the technique manoeuvres' parameters were successful in reducing pain and impairment. Research validates H1, the experimental hypothesis. There was a substantial difference in both the NDI score and BQ score between the two types of therapy. The study finds that group B, or deep friction friction massage therapy, reduced pain and disability more than SNAGs, as evidenced by the difference in BQ and NDI from the first to the 21st day (Table No. 4-4) for both groups/therapies.

LIMITATIONS

1. It must be large sample to generalize the value of this test.
2. Study was performed with only mobility deficit and mechanical neck pain.
3. The study is limited to age group of 16-25 years.
4. Furthermore, the absence of a blind assessor was another point that caused the bias.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. NDI and BQ can be used as primary outcome to measure (ROM) of the neck movement for further study.
2. The comparison between SNAG and DTFM techniques on other joints of spinal regions would be done for further study.

A Comparative Study on The Effect of Snags Versus Deep Transverse Friction Massage on The Students with Mechanical Neck Pain and Mobility Deficit

3. The comparison between Sustained Natural Apophyseal Glides and circular Friction Massage techniques would be done for further study.
4. MMT can be used as primary outcome to measure the strength of a neck muscles for further study.

RERERENCES

- [1] Khan T. Risk factors of mechanical neck pain among students (doctoral dissertation, bangladesh health professions institute, faculty of medicine, the University of Dhaka, bangladesh).
- [2] Gull m, khalil w, jaffar m, ara j, mustansar a, laiue t. Prevalence of mechanical neck pain among university students: an observational study.
- [3] Satria MH, antari NA, saraswati NL. The efficacy of muscle energy technique in individuals with mechanical neck pain: a systematic review. *Sport fit J.* 2020;8(2):91-8.
- [4] Varshney K, raghav S, singh A. A study to compare the effect of positional release technique (PRT) versus deep transverse friction massage (DTFM) on pain and disability in patients with mechanical neck pain.
- [5] Khokhar SR, stern Y, bell K, anderson K, noe E, mayeux R, albert SM. Persistent mobility deficit in the absence of deficits in activities of daily living: a risk factor for mortality. *Journal of the american geriatrics society.* 2001 nov;49(11):1539-43.
- [6] Pal A, misra A. Effectiveness of snag mobilization on computer professionals with mechanical neck pain and mobility deficit. *Int J physiother res.* 2019;7(2):3022-27.
- [7] Paquin JP, tousignant-laflamme Y, dumas JP. Effects of SNAG mobilization combined with a self-snag home-exercise for the treatment of cervicogenic headache: a pilot study. *Journal of manual & manipulative therapy.* 2021 jul 4;29(4):244-54.
- [8] Saleh AM, abdel-aal NM, ibrahem OA. Mobilization with movement versus thoracic manipulation on neck proprioception in mechanical neck pain: A randomized controlled study. *Journal of pharmaceutical negative results.* 2023 may 25:3972-80.
- [9] Tachii R, sen S, arfath U. Short-term effect of sustained natural apophyseal glides on cervical joint position sense, pain and neck disability in patients with chronic neck pain. *International journal of therapies and rehabilitation research.* 2015;4(5):244.
- [10] Shamsi S, alyazedi FM, abdelkader SM, khan S, akhtar A. Efficacy of sustained natural apophyseal glides in the management of mechanical neck pain: A randomized clinical trial. *Indian journal of medical specialities.* 2021 oct 1; 12(4):199-206.
- [11] VIJAYAN K, MAN AS, kumaresan PA, PALANI JL. Short-term effect of mulligan snags on pain intensity, cervical range of motion and craniovertebral angle in patients with nonspecific neck pain: A quasi-experimental study. *Journal of clinical & diagnostic research.* 2022 jul 1; 16(7).

- [12] Farooq MN, mohseni-bandpei MA, gilani SA, ashfaq M, mahmood Q. The effects of neck mobilization in patients with chronic neck pain: A randomized controlled trial. *Journal of bodywork and movement therapies*. 2018 jan 1; 22(1):24-31.
- [13] Ganesh GS, mohanty P, pattnaik M, mishra C. Effectiveness of mobilization therapy and exercises in mechanical neck pain. *Physiotherapy theory and practice*. 2015 feb 17; 31(2):99-106.
- [14] Mohamed EE, kotb abd elrazik R. Sustained natural apophyseal glides versus positional release therapy in the treatment of chronic mechanical neck dysfunction. *International journal of human movement and sports sciences*. 2020; 8(6):384-94.
- [15] González rueda V, lópez de celis C, barra lópez ME, carrasco uribarren A, castillo tomás S, hidalgo garcía C. Effectiveness of a specific manual approach to the suboccipital region in patients with chronic mechanical neck pain and rotation deficit in the upper cervical spine: study protocol for a randomized controlled trial. *BMC musculoskeletal disorders*. 2017 dec; 18(1):1-8.
- [16] De zoete RM, brown L, oliveira K, penglaze L, rex R, sawtell B, sullivan T. The effectiveness of general physical exercise for individuals with chronic neck pain: a systematic review of randomised controlled trials. *European journal of physiotherapy*. 2020 may 3; 22(3):141-7.
- [17] Vicenzino B, paungmali A, teys P. Mulligan's mobilization-with-movement, positional faults and pain relief: current concepts from a critical review of literature. *Manual therapy*. 2007 may 1; 12(2):98-108.
- [18] Varshney K, Raghav S, Singh A. A study to compare the effect of positional release technique (PRT) versus deep transverse friction massage (DTFM) on pain and disability in patients with mechanical neck pain. *International Journal of Yoga, Physiotherapy and Physical Education*. 2020;5(2):16
- [19] Tuğral A, Çam Y. Potential Role of Smartphone Addiction on Sleep Quality and Perceived Neck Pain Among Undergraduate Physiotherapy Students: A Multicentered Cross-Sectional Study. *Ergoterapi ve Rehabilitasyon Dergisi*. 2024 Jul 5;12(2):61-70.
- [20] Jorritsma W, Dijkstra PU, de Vries GE, Geertzen JH, Reneman MF. Detecting relevant changes and responsiveness of neck pain and disability scale and neck disability index. *European Spine Journal*. 2012 Dec; 21:2550-7.
- [21] Howell ER. The association between neck pain, the Neck Disability Index and cervical ranges of motion: a narrative review. *The Journal of the Canadian Chiropractic Association*. 2011 Sep;55(3):211.
- [22] Khan S, Arsh A, Khan S, Ali S. Deep transverse friction massage in the management of adhesive capsulitis: A systematic review. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*. 2024 Jan;40(3Part-II):526.

A Comparative Study on The Effect of Snags Versus Deep Transverse Friction Massage on The Students with Mechanical Neck Pain and Mobility Deficit

- [23] La Touche R, Fernández-de-Las-Peñas C, Fernández-Carnero J, Díaz-Parreño S, Paris-Alemany A, Arendt-Nielsen L. Bilateral mechanical-pain sensitivity over the trigeminal region in patients with chronic mechanical neck pain. *The Journal of Pain*. 2010 Mar 1;11(3):256-63.
- [24] Aragón-Basanta E, Venegas W, Ayala G, Page A, Serra-Añó P. Relationship between neck kinematics and neck disability index. An approach based on functional regression. *Scientific Reports*. 2024 Jan 2;14(1):215
- [25] ABDELMEGEED M, AISHA S, YOUSSEF EF. Relationship between Pain, Functional Disability, Proprioception, and Scapular Muscle Strength in Patients with Chronic Mechanical Neck Pain. *The Medical Journal of Cairo University*. 2024 Dec 1;91(12):1435-41.
- [26] Ozlu O, Sahin M. The effect of mulligan mobilization technique application in addition to conventional physiotherapy on pain and joint range of motion in people with neck pain. *Journal of Bodywork and Movement Therapies*. 2024 Jul 1; 39:225-30.
- [27] Mohamed MA, Hafez HA. Effect Of Home Exercise Program Versus Stretching Program on Chest Expansion For Patients With Chronic Mechanical Neck Pain. *Egyptian Journal of Physical Therapy*. 2024 Mar 1;17(1).
- [28] Sun X, Chai L, Huang Q, Zhou H, Liu H. Effects of exercise combined with cervicothoracic spine self-mobilization on chronic non-specific neck pain. *Scientific Reports*. 2024 Mar 4;14(1):1

Citation: Sonam Nidhi and Sunny Kumar, A Comparative Study on The Effect of Snags Versus Deep Transverse Friction Massage on The Students with Mechanical Neck Pain and Mobility Deficit, *International Journal of Physiotherapy (IJPH)* 2(2), 2024, pp. 1–10

Abstract Link: https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJPH_02_02_001

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJPH/VOLUME_2_ISSUE_2/IJPH_02_02_001.pdf

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

editor@iaeme.com